

DESIGNED LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERN COMPUTER LEARNING AID

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Abstract: The use of computers in teaching and overtime work is an effective way to improve motivation and individualization of instruction. Integration of usual lesson with a computer allows the teacher to shift part of their work on the computer, while the learning process becomes more interesting and intense. The computer does not replace the teacher, but only complements it. The use of computer technology makes the lesson more exciting and allows to make an informed choice for best training.

Key words: computer technologies, foreign language, computer program, affects, principles, structure, teaching methods, experience.

Analysis of material which is discussed on international scientific conferences shows us that the purpose of education is not just knowledge and skills, but also definite qualities of personality. Post-industrial society is interested in the ability to make decisions, adapt to varying conditions of life, act on one's own, etc.

However, according to the opinion of E.S. Polat, who is the author of research on teaching foreign languages, including the method of projects, «solution of these tasks was rather difficult because of absence of real conditions for carrying out, in consideration of traditional approach to education which focuses on class-lessons system" [16; 13]. She supposes that the main task of school does not consist in the content of education, but in the use of new technologies of teaching.

Let us take the concept of "projecting" (Latin "projectus" - thrown ahead). Speaking about it, we should pay attention to the fact that this is not a new word in pedagogical theory. This definition appeared at the end of the 70-s in the context of the new program which was offered by the Royal College of Art in Great Britain.

Relying on notions of projecting and technologies of teaching, Polat considers methodology of projects as a complex of recognition, problem, creative methods which develop imagination and at the same time they form personality of pupils [16; 67].

Nowadays we have a computer era here. And the function of projects is carried out by many programs and one of them is Microsoft Power Point. This innovation device includes the best experience of the past and something completely new and effective of our present. Sure, the advent of new technologies in the learning process is always exciting. They add new dimensions to the class and spark students to a higher level of motivation and achievement.

Analysis of experimental investigations in this sphere is evidence of conclusion that we need such teaching material, that could take into account all peculiarities and problems which we face during the process of teaching. Many authors (Carol A. Pope, Jeffrey N. Golub) find Power Point as a tool which is able to stimulate the study of foreign languages and consider it as a key to the growth of achievements of pupils.

J. Bush criticizes this point of view. He says: "Regardless of the cool transitions, laser-letter effects, and snappy backgrounds, a PowerPoint presentation that passes on information is not much different than a chalkboard and overhead lecture". However, we can't agree with him. The matter is that comprehension of grammatical and lexical units of foreign language often causes some difficulties for pupils who study it.

Many methodologists assumed that at first children do not learn the relationship between a sign and a meaning, but they learn the connection between a word and a subject. It happens automatically because of our conditional reflex and also because of just simple contact between two irritants.

Each presentation is a workbook of teaching material on specific topics. The biggest advantage of this program consists in, that a teacher can use prepared presentation as a whole in part. It depends on a teacher and objectives of a lesson.

This technology allows to successfully combine different forms of organization of the educational process. It promotes better interaction among pupils and also the role of a teacher takes another position. Instead of a supervisor, he becomes an equal partner and adviser who is always ready to help in mastering a foreign language.

The wide usage of illustrations and Flash-animations in the presentations of this program allows to present all the vocabulary of the lesson quite easily and understandably. The great advantage of this means is that we don't need to translate all words in English. Foreign words are associated with pictures and they stay in the memory for a long time.

Stage of imposition of new words begins on the separate slide. Each unit of vocabulary is processed phonetically with the help of wave files. It allows you to repeat difficult lexical units as many times as you need.

Thanks to this program, the graphic of the word forms immediately with its sound image. Such means of entering new vocabulary takes into consideration the personality of each pupil - those who have aural memory and also whose memory is visual.

After that the meaning of each lexical unit is opened and examples of its usage are given in the form of word combinations and sentences. It will be the stage of explanation and use of learned material on practice. In presentations of this kind, we use the most popular way of semanticization of vocabulary - demonstration of a picture in the case when we deal with the words that mean concrete subjects.

Explanation of complicated grammatical rules turns into exiting adventure which guarantees high level of understanding. Also, perfect results can be reached because of cognitive interest of pupils and their desire for everything new. For example, real facts about different animals from the Guinness World Records not only open one's mind but also stimulate usage of knowledge on this topic.

Repeated playback of educational situations and interactive use of visual methods allow to realize the principle of better digestion of knowledge. Usage of multimedia technologies favors rise of motivation, reduction of bad marks and better knowledge of foreign languages.

We can't keep from mentioning the technical advantage of listening with the help of Power Point, which allows the teacher to repeat the material as much as he needs without loss of time because the audio file is always ready for replaying and you don't need to rewind the tape again and again. Besides, a teacher isn't obliged to put all notes on the black board. All preparation for listening and necessary material can fit one slide in the form of controlling buttons, variety of effects of animation and accompanying sound.

Information which is presented as Power Point presentation increases opportunities of ordinary textbooks because of sound, video and animation. During the work with a computer pupils use hearing and sight, and they allow to increase not only the volume of perceptible information but also the quality of memory.

It should be mentioned, that in the case if a teacher uses designed language teaching methodology, he acquires another role and function in the

teaching process. Designed education, especially thanks to new computer technologies, substitutes the traditional paradigm of teaching foreign languages. Thereby, projecting helps pupils to realize the role of knowledge in life and in the process of studying. Knowledge stops being an aim, it becomes the means of true education.

Contemporary pedagogical technologies such as teaching in cooperation, project method, using new informational technologies, Internet resources help to realize personal orientational approach in teaching, support individualization and differentiation of teaching in calculation with students' abilities, their pre-higher educational preparation level, inclination and etc. According to E. Polat, informational technologies contribute to increase academic motivation of teaching foreign languages and advance pupils' knowledge. Use of computer during English lessons significantly increases academic process intensity. Computer teaching assimilates a large amount of material, then it was acquired using traditional teaching conditions. Besides material in using computer is acquired more substantially. Computer supplies multi supporting, that is current, intermediate, total academic process control. Computer supplies multi supporting control of academic process that is current intermediate, total. Using the computer control of quality students' knowledge to achieve the large objectiveness of valuation. Besides, computer control considerably economizes academic time, as it checks students' knowledge simultaneously.

Such cooperation suggests control six methodically important summons of pupil as personality context activity, personal experience, wish, interest, inclination sphere, emotional perceptual sphere, worldview, pupil's status in the group. All these instigate pupils to learn.

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